

QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION OF THE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS BEHAVIOR OF CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITES BY SQUID-NDI METHOD

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SUMMARY: The compact tension (CT) and double-edge-notched (DEN) geometry were used to investigate the fracture behavior and toughening mechanisms of cross-ply-laminated carbon/carbon (C/C) composites. The 2D C/C composite exhibited an interesting "zigzag cracking" during growth of the damage in the 0° plies. At the same time, a straight splitting extension was formed in the 90° plies. This zigzag crack proceeded in the following order, at first vertical splitting were formed, then micro-cracks between the splitting were existed, and finally a connectedly unstable crack was propagated. A stable/unstable regime of the zigzag cracking was repeated for several cycles until the complete failure of the specimens. An R-curve was determined, taking this cracking extension into consideration. The R-curve demonstrated that the high-fracture toughness of the cross-ply laminated C/C composites could be attributed due to the zigzag cracking characteristics. Then, the DEN results were compared with the R-curve behavior. This comparison showed that the DEN occurred at the initial value of the R-curve obtained when the micro-crack growth length was regarded as the crack tip. In addition, based on the electrically conductive characteristics of C/C composites, superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) method was adopted to detect the damaged area and damage degree of defects in C/C composites.

KEYWORDS: Carbon/carbon composites, splitting, micro-cracks, zigzag crack, R-curve, fracture toughness, SQUID-NDE

INTRODUCTION

Carbon/carbon, C/C, composites have received an increasing attention in recent years as potential materials for advanced high-temperature applications in several space industries [1-3]. This increase in attention arose mainly due to the unique properties of C/C composites. High fracture toughness is an important advantage of C/C composites [4]. Compared with monolithic ceramics, C/C composites possess nearly one order of magnitude of fracture toughness higher than that of ceramics [5]. Many research have been made to identify the damage processes and toughening mechanisms of C/C composites [6-10]. According to the recent literatures [6,8-10], it has been widely accepted that the ability of C/C composites to redistribute stresses near notch tips is due to the shear band formation mechanism. This shear damage band might extend perpendicular to the notch direction under mode I remote loading. Such damage emanates from the edge of a notch and leads to the reduction of stress concentration ahead of the notch. This damage mechanism enhances crack extension resistance by

shielding the crack tip from the applied load. The low shear/tensile strength ratio and weak fiber/matrix interface of C/C composites [6] are thought to be responsible for this behavior. However, the shear bands have rarely been observed in C/C composites on either the microscopic or the macroscopic scale [11-16].

A better understanding of the damage growth within C/C composites is necessary in order to clarify the source mechanisms of notch insensitivity and high fracture toughness; such an explanation would then help to improve structural performance via the design process. In the present study, the process of damage development in 2D C/C was clarified to better understand of high fracture toughness behavior and notch insensitivity. Compact tension and double-edge-notch tests were carried out in cross-ply laminated C/C composites, and the crack extension resistance (R-) curve behavior was obtained. The R-curve behavior was then related to fracture process.

Since using the conventionally non-destructive evaluation, NDE, techniques for detecting the development of the fracture damage in C/C composites are extremely difficult, rather NDE technique by means of superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) was examined in this study. The intent of examining this NDE technique is mainly for exploring an effective method for the practically structural components made of C/C composites. To achieve this purpose, the SQUID technique was explored to clarify the damage mechanisms that controlled the high fracture toughness and notch insensitivity of 2D C/C composites.

MATERIALS

In the present work, 2D C/C composite reinforced with high-modulus carbon fibers, Torayca® M40 PAN-based, produced by Toray Industries, Inc., Japan were examined. This composite was produced via a preformed yarn method (Across Co. Ltd. Japan). In the preformed yarn method, bundles of the carbon fibers (6K) and powders of matrix precursor (coke and bulk mesophase pitch) were placed into thin nylon sheaths. These sheathed bundles were arranged unidirectionally and stitched together with thin nylon filament in order to produce an UD-preformed sheet. Then, in the present case, sixteen preformed-sheets were laminated (crossed over each other) into a symmetric cross-ply stacking sequence 1:1 to form a green cross-ply C/C composites. Finally, the preformed plies were hot-pressed in a mold at 600 °C for carbonization, followed by heat treatment at a temperature of 2000 °C for graphitization in an inert atmosphere to yield cross-ply laminated C/C composite. The volume fraction of the fiber in this C/C composite was about 50% and the mechanical properties are listed in Table I.

Table 1. Mechanical and physical properties of examined 2D C/C composites.

C/C Composite Type	Tensile Strength [MPa]	Young's Modulus [GPa]	Shear Strength [MPa]	Shear Modulus [GPa]	Poison's Ratio	Density [gm/cm ³]	Fiber Volume Fraction
2D C/C composites	180.3	90.2	31.9	5.4	0.026	1.69	0.5

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Fracture Toughness Measurement

The compact tension (CT) tests and tensile tests of double-edge-notch (DEN) specimens were performed using a screw-driven mechanical testing machine (Autograph AG-5000G, Shimadzu Corp., Japan) under a cross-head speed of 0.1 mm/min.

Compact Tension Test

The compact tension, CT, tests were carried out to observe the damage growth and to obtain the

resistance-curve, R-curve in the cross-ply-laminated C/C composites. The configuration of the CT specimens was based on ASTM Standard E-399-72, where the crack length-to-size ratio, a/W , was about 0.5. This pre-crack was introduced at first by a diamond wheel with a thickness of 0.4 mm, and then the notch tip was sharpened by a fresh razor blade to a size of 0.1 mm. The C/C composites are known to be insensitive to a notch tip radius within a range of 0-2 mm [12]. In order to observe damage growth in the differently angled plies in the 2D C/C composites, two types of CT specimen configurations were prepared. The first type had a pre-introduced crack running in the same direction as the fibers in the surface plies, whereas the other type run perpendicular to the direction of the surface ply fibers. To observe the process of damage extension by CT test, the samples were polished using diamond-past of 15 μm diameter, degreased in ethanol and cleaned in an ultrasonic bath, dried at room temperature, and then thinly painted white. The damage process was observed from both sides of the specimens using a travelling optical microscope with a magnification of 25 and a CCD camera during the CT test. A clip gage (UB-5, Tokyo-Sokki Crop, Japan) was used to measure the crack opening displacement (COD). Two acoustic emission sensors (AE-900M-WE, NF Electric Instruments Crop, Japan) were attached on the CT specimen to provide signals for the damage formation. Compact tension tests were conducted by repeating the loading-unloading cycles.

Double-Edge-Notch Test

Double-Edge Notch (DEN) specimens and smooth specimens were prepared to evaluate the adequacy of the CT results as a fracture toughness criterion. In both specimens, the loading direction was set to the fiber direction of the surface plies. In the DEN specimens, a ratio of total notch length to specimen width ($2a/W$) was fixed at 0.5, and the width of the specimen (W) fell within a range of 8 mm to 24 mm. Tapered aluminum tabs were glued by epoxy adhesive at the grip portions of the DEN and smooth specimens.

R-curve Evaluation

A compliance method was used to determine the crack growth resistance (R-) curve of CT test specimens by applying the linear elastic fracture mechanics to estimate the energy release rate of C/C composites [11] by the following equation;

$$G_{IR} = \frac{P^2}{2B} \frac{dC_{pin}}{da}, \quad (1)$$

where P , B , C_{pin} , and a are the load at each crack increment, CT specimen thickness, compliance measured at the loading point, and crack growth length, respectively. The compliance was determined based on crack opening displacement, COD, at the load axis. Next, energy release rate G_{IR} obtained by Equation (1) was converted into the stress intensity factor K_I by use of the following equation:

$$G_{IR} = K_I^2 \sqrt{\frac{S_{11}S_{22}}{2}} \left[\sqrt{\frac{S_{22}}{S_{11}}} + \frac{2S_{12} + S_{66}}{2S_{11}} \right]^{1/2}, \quad (2)$$

where S_{ij} are the components of the compliance tensor. Using the material constants shown in Table 1, the tensor components were determined as follows;

$$\begin{aligned} S_{11} &= 1/E_{11}; & S_{12} &= -\nu_{12}/E_{11} \\ S_{22} &= 1/E_{22}; & S_{66} &= 1/G_{12} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Finite Element Modeling

The loading axis COD and compliance of the CT specimens during tensile loading were determined using the finite element method (FEM) for a model that simulates half of the CT configuration under

the assumption of a linear anisotropic plane stress condition. The mesh of this model is composed of biquadratic elements with eight-nodes. In this model, a concentrated load is applied at the pinhole of the CT configuration.

In addition, Finite element calculations were performed to determine stress intensity factors for DEN specimens. The stress intensity factors were determined using virtual crack closure method [17] under the assumption of a linear anisotropic plane stress condition and also under the assumption of a linear isotropic plane stress condition to determine the anisotropy factor (H). The material properties used in the FEM calculations are listed in Table I. The FEM calculations were carried out using a commercial code, ABAQUS version 5.8.

Fracture Toughness Evaluation

The critical stress intensity factors of the used C/C composites were determined from the net fracture stress and the pre-crack length of the DEN specimens by use of the following Equations [18].

$$K_I = \sigma \sqrt{\pi a} f(\xi) \quad (4)$$

$$f(\xi) = \frac{1.122 - 0.561\xi - 0.205\xi^2 + 0.471\xi^3 - 0.19\xi^4}{\sqrt{1-\xi}} \quad (5)$$

where σ is fracture tensile stress, a is pre-crack length, and $\xi = 2a/W = 0.5$.

Equation 4 is for isotropic material systems. Many detailed studies were conducted on composite systems to analyze the error introduced by using the isotropic rather than the orthotropic shape factor. For this purpose, additional parameter, H , the anisotropy factor, has been introduced by Konish [19], and defined as the ratio of anisotropic stress intensity factor to its isotropic counterpart. The anisotropy factor, H , is thus formulated as.

$$H = \xi_{(\text{orthotropic})} / \xi_{(\text{isotropic})} = K_{I(\text{orthotropic})} / K_{I(\text{isotropic})} \quad (6)$$

The influence of material anisotropy on the stress intensity factor can be directly measured in terms of the deviation of H from its isotropic value of unity. The values of the anisotropy factor depend on both specimen geometry and the material properties. The anisotropy factor, H , of DEN configuration of the present 2D C/C composites has been calculated by calculating both isotropic and anisotropic K_I , that calculated using virtual crack closure method by means of FEM. The value of the present material factor is about 0.945.

Superconducting Quantum Interference Device (SQUID) Monitoring

The high electrical conductivity of both constituents of C/C composites, carbon fibers and carbon matrix, enables the electrical resistivity of C/C composites to change in response to damage, thereby damage sensing in C/C composites using the magnetic field might be effected. SQUID (Superconducting Quantum Interference Device) is a highly sensitive magnetic sensor. SQUID utilizes the quantum effect of superconductivity and is more than three orders higher in sensitivity than conventional magnetic sensors [22-23]. This high sensitivity prompts its application to detection of the internal and subsurface flaws, in ferromagnetic nonferromagnetic conducting materials [22].

Current Detection Method

In the neighborhood of an isolated and concentrated current \mathbf{I} flowing in x-y plane, field gradient dB_z/dy and dB_z/dx are approximately proportional to x- and y- components of the current I_x and I_y respectively, according to Maxwell's equation $\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \mu \mathbf{J}$. In the case of current flowing uniformly in

a plate specimen with wide x-y plane, the field gradient dB_z/dy and dB_z/dx due to the current is almost constant, nearly zero, except near the edge of the specimen. A local defect in such specimen causes change of current around the defect, ΔI_x and ΔI_y . The field gradient induced by such local current change occurred in uniform current should be approximately equivalent to that by the isolated and concentrated current. Thus the field gradient dB_z/dy and dB_z/dx due to the local current change are roughly proportional to ΔI_x and ΔI_y respectively. So we adopted a SQUID gradiometer to detect directly the detoured current due to damage in specimen. A detoured current map can be obtained by converting measured dB_z/dy and dB_z/dx into ΔI_x and ΔI_y .

Fig. 1. The principle of SQUID system.

SQUID System and Measurements

In-house low critical temperature (LTS) SQUID-NDE system, constructed in National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST) [24-25], was used in this study for damage detection of notched C/C composites, CT specimens with $W=120$ mm for 2D C/C composites. This system is composed of low- T_c SQUID sensor, first-order planar gradiometer (pick-up coils), SQUID electronics, Helium dewar, x-y scanning stage, lock-in amplifier, and PC as shown in Fig. 1. More details of this system are described elsewhere [24].

At first, sinusoidal current of 90 mA with low frequency of 710 Hz was injected into undamaged CT specimen in x direction. Then, the field gradients dB_z/dx and dB_z/dy above the specimen are measured with lift-off distance of 4.5 mm and sampling space of 2 mm in x- and y-directions. This is the procedure of field gradient measurement. After the measurements, we applied the tensile load to the CT specimen in y-direction, to make the damage condition of the splitting stage. After unloading the CT specimen, we applied the procedure of field gradient measurement to the damaged specimen. As well as the splitting stage, the micro-cracks and unstable zigzag crack stages were made successively, and the procedure was repeated. The procedure was carried out adopting the same lift-off and scanning area.

Fig. 2. Terminal settings and scanned area on CT specimen for SQUID-NDE.

To eliminate the background signals and to decrease the field gradient due to uniform current, current return pad (unflawed conducting sheet made of copper) was placed beneath and parallel to the CT sample and this sheet was electrically connected in series at one end with the sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Load-COD Curve

Loading/unloading cycle tests were conducted to determine crack extension resistance, G_R , as a function of crack growth length using CT test specimens. Partial unloading was carried out during compact tension, CT test. This non-complete unloading is to avoid excess energy dissipation in the frontal process zone [20]. It is noted from this load-COD curve that a slight non-linearity was initiated before the maximum load was applied in the first cycle, and the load dropped abruptly at the maximum load of each cycle.

Damage Evolution

The CT tests demonstrated that damage growth on the surfaces of 2D C/C composites depended on the fiber reinforcement direction. For example, when the fiber reinforcement direction of the surface plies was parallel to the pre-introduced crack (90° plies), a straight crack without fiber failure extended horizontally from the pre-notch tip. On the other hand, when the surface ply fibers ran normal to the pre-introduced crack (0° plies), the initial damage observed during tensile loading in the CT samples was commonly called "splitting" (Fig. 3). The splitting was identified as widely opened transverse cracks. The transverse cracks were induced during the cooling stage after the processing of the C/C composites. When the applied load was increased, the splitting did not grow; however many micro-cracks appeared between the splits in the 0° ply, as shown in Fig. 3. Micro-cracks were located near ends of 0° ply splitting and on splitting in the adjacent 90° plies, as shown in Fig. 3. This tendency indicated that the micro-cracks were induced by stress concentration due to a combination of splitting in the 0° ply and the adjacent 90° ply. With a further increase in load, the number of micro-cracks increased, and the splitting in a 0° ply and micro-cracks eventually joined to form a large crack extension that included fiber fracture. This extension facilitated additional formation of splitting and micro-cracks ahead of the large crack, as shown in Fig. 3. By repeating this process, fiber fracture extended across the ligament. Thus, unstable macro-zigzag cracking occurred.

Figure 4 depicts the applied load and the acoustic-emission (AE) event rates as a function of crack opening displacement during the first loading of a cyclic CT test. It should be noted that in this Figure, the multiple splitting gave rise to a non-linear load-COD relationship, and unstable crack growth induced a rapid load drop. In order to reveal the damage pattern in the interior plies, the tested CT specimens were sectioned and polished with 3 μm diamond paste. Then, the microstructures of the cross-sections were observed using a polarized light optical microscope. It follows that the cracks in the 0° and 90° plies passed individually through nearly the same vertical locations and they were connected by inter-laminar delamination between the 0° and 90° plies. This result indicated that the zigzag cracks had formed in all of the 0° plies, whereas in all of the 90° plies straight splitting prevailed, parallel to the pre-crack direction.

Resistance Curve (R-curve)

An apparent R-curve (Fig. 5) was obtained by applying the compliance approach. The crack growth length in this Figure was determined from the 90° surface plies. This figure shows that fracture resistance rapidly increased from the initiation value of 7.6 MPa.m^{1/2} to a saturation value of about 20 MPa.m^{1/2}.

As regards the zigzag crack growth, it appears necessary to take into account the influence of the cyclic stable/unstable transition of crack extension on the R-curve, because the 0° plies sustained most of load. Thus, 0° plies were the focus of the study. Figure 6 shows compliance as a function of crack

Increase of load

Fig. 3. Fracture behavior of 2D C/C composites.

Fig. 4. Load versus crack opening displacement of 2D C/C composites.

length in the 0° and 90° plies, where crack length was determined by the observed splitting in the 0° and 90° plies, by the micro-cracks, and by the unstable-crack in 0° ply. In this Figure, the calculated crack lengths are also shown. Only a small fraction of the 0° fibers might have failed during the micro-crack growth; however, all of the fibers fractured during unstable crack growth. To evaluate which crack front was better for use in the determination of the R-curve, the initiations of the micro-cracks and the unstable crack, illustrated in Fig. 6, were chosen.

The resulting R-curves are shown in Fig. 7. It became obvious that crack extension, based on the micro-crack, yielded a periodically fluctuating R-curve. In the first cycle, fracture resistance, based on the micro-crack, rapidly increased from the initiation value of $9.7 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ to a maximum value of about $20 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$. From the next cycles, the initial values were higher than of that of the first cycle. This difference of the initial values is due to existence of splits and micro-cracks at the initial stages of the subsequent higher cycles. In the case of the unstable R-curve, as shown in Fig. 7, the initial and saturated values were almost similar to the maximum value of the micro-crack R-curve, i.e., no rising R-curve was observed for an unstable R-curve representation. This finding indicated that the rising R-curve, high fracture toughness, in 2D C/C composites was yielded during the micro-crack formation concomitant with zigzag damage.

Fracture Toughness Criterion

The net tensile fracture stresses of the DEN specimens versus the pre-crack lengths are shown in Fig. 8. This figure shows clearly that the fracture stress was higher or lower than that of the averaged stress of the smooth specimens when the pre-crack length is short or long, respectively. The averaged stress of the smooth specimens was determined in over 10 specimens and was confirmed to be independent of specimen width [12]. In Figure 8, the dotted and dashed lines were determined by the fracture toughness criterion using the initial values of both R-curves that had been obtained based on the crack extension lengths of the 90° and 0° (micro-cracks in the zigzag cracking) surface plies, respectively. The best fit obtained by the fracture toughness criterion with the experimental DEN results, solid line, was yielded at a stress intensity factor of $11 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$. This value was slightly higher than the crack extension resistance based on micro-crack growth (zigzag crack). Precisely, fracture of materials should be determined using the entire R-curve as has previously been discussed by Broek [21]. This approach should resolve this slight discrepancy. From the above results, it can be concluded that the splitting and micro-cracks formation during the zigzag cracking is effective toughening mechanism controlling the fracture of DEN specimens. However, the splitting and micro-cracks are small-scaled and slight damage. This is why we could not identify the damage near the

Fig. 5. R-curve based on damage in 90° plies of 2D C/C composites.

Fig. 6. Compliance as a function of crack growth lengths of splitting, micro-cracks, and unstable crack as well as calculated length by FEM.

Fig. 7. Zigzag R-curves as a function of the tensile growth band of micro-cracks and unstable crack respectively.

crack tips of the DEN specimens in the previous reports [13-14].

SQUID Results

Damage Detection of 2D C/C Composites

Figure 9 (a)~(d) show the current maps of the scanned areas of undamaged CT sample, stage of splitting formation, stage of micro-cracks formation, and stage of unstable zigzag crack respectively in the case of current injection in plus x-direction. The magnitude and direction of the vector arrows in these figures show the intensity and direction of the current. Current flowing in minus x-direction means decrease from the uniformly injected current due to defect. If splitting in y-direction exists, currents should direct toward plus or minus y-direction in front of the splitting, and currents toward minus x-direction appear behind the splitting. Minimum value of the contour lines is determined by adding system noise and average value of the currents in non-damaged area of 10 mm x 10 mm enough far from the pre-crack and edges of the specimen. It is assumed that the degree of defect and the defected area can be represented by the minimum contour lines area of the amount of the detoured current and total amount of the detoured current, respectively.

In Fig. 9a, the currents toward minus x-direction near the pre-crack are due to the pre-crack. The currents at upper side of the pre-crack are supposed to be detoured due to a small transverse crack in 0° plies. In Fig. 9b, the detoured current area significantly increases compared with the initial stage. In this stage, two splitting in y-direction were observed microscopically at 4 mm and 8 mm from the crack tip, with 8 mm and 2 mm lengths, respectively. Vertical arrows as shown in Fig. 9b indicate the positions of the observed splitting microscopically. The location of the former roughly agrees with where the currents toward plus y-direction appear at upper side of the pre-crack tip. The location of the latter agrees with where the currents toward minus y-direction appear ahead of the pre-crack. However, in this figure more currents toward minus y-direction can be found ahead of the pre-crack tip by about 20 mm. This means more splitting was happened ahead the pre-crack tip but that was unobserved microscopically. In Fig. 9c, the detoured current area extends a little toward plus y-direction and the intensity of detoured current at lower side of the pre-crack is increased. It can be supposed roughly that this behavior was occurred due to the micro-cracks formation in those regions. The splitting of 8-mm length newly appeared at 10 mm from the right edge at the second stage. The location of this splitting agrees with the extended area of the detoured current. The splitting at 8mm extended it length to about 4mm. However, the defects extending toward x-direction should be detected in principle when the current injects in minus y-

Fig. 8. Net fracture stress of DEN specimens as a function of pre-crack

Fig. 9. Current maps obtained by current injection uniformly in x-direction. (a) at the initial stage, (b) at the splitting formation stage, (c) at the micro-cracks formation stage, and (d) at the unstable zigzag crack formation.

direction into the CT specimen.

In Fig. 9d, the area of the detoured currents extends toward minus y-direction and a little toward minus x-direction. The splitting at 4 mm extends to 20 mm. The splitting at 8 mm extends to 10 mm toward minus y-direction. The splitting at 10 mm extends to 6 mm long. The change of the detoured current area approximately corresponds to the extension or occurrence of the splitting. We should be able to roughly estimate the location and extended length of the splitting from the detoured current map.

Fig. 10. (a) The relationship between the detoured current area and the damage stage. (b) The relationship between the total amount of the detoured current and the damage stage.

The relationship between the damaged area and the damage stage, obtained from Fig. 9, is shown in Fig. 10a. The area increases roughly linearly as the stage advances except for the initial stage. Figure 10b shows the relationship between the total current amount in the detoured current area and the damage stage. The increase of the amount from the micro-cracks to unstable zigzag crack stages is much larger than the increase from the splitting to micro-cracks stages. It is supposed that this difference should be due to the delamination and unstable crack that occurred.

CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusions of the present study are as follows.

1. Zigzag cracking occurred in 0° plies in cross-ply C/C composite. One cycle of zigzag cracking proceeded in the following order, i.e., at first vertical splits were observed, then micro-cracks between those splits, and finally unstable crack growth connected the micro-cracks and splits.
2. This stable/unstable regime of zigzag cracking was repeated.
3. A zigzag R-curve represented the intrinsic toughness of cross-ply laminated C/C composites.
4. The high-fracture toughness of the cross-ply laminated C/C composites was attributed to the zigzag cracking characteristics.
5. The area and amount of detoured current obtained by SQUID due to splitting in y-direction were successfully detected with current injection in x-direction.
6. SQUID can detect the very small size of the splitting which are undetectable by both of microscopic observations and the other NDE methods.
7. Matrix cracks induced either upon processing or during testing were found to have a strong influence on the toughening mechanism of the cross-ply laminated C/C composites.

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